

WORKING OUT THE OPTIMAL CONDITIONS FOR OBTAINING IMPORT-SUBSTITUTING POLYMER SULFUR FOR THE OIL AND GAS AND RUBBER INDUSTRY

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Abstract. The scientific significance of the research result - the physical and mechanical properties of elementary sulfur produced at the Mubarak gas processing plant was studied on the basis of propantriol (glycerin), lower molecular polyethylene, phenol and aniline, polymer sulfur. With the participation of modifiers, the effect of sulfur/modifier ratio, reaction temperature and time on polymer sulfur production yield was determined. To study physical and mechanical properties of synthesized polymer sulfur, methods ISO 8332, ASTM D4569, ASTM D4574 were used.

Keywords: deformation, polymer, copolymer, polysulfide, adhesion, destruction, ash level, modifier, toluene, amorphous, styrene, stability.

Introduction. It is known that today in our country, polymer sulfur necessary for rubber, oil and gas, road industry is imported from abroad at the expense of foreign currency. Currently, thousands of tons of technical sulfur are constantly accumulating and increasing in the oil and gas processing industry, causing environmental problems by polluting the environment [1]. Polymer sulfur production solves the problem of their polymer sulfur for the highway, oil and gas, rubber engineering industries [2]. According to the literature, polymer contains three important processes in determining the optimal conditions for obtaining sulfur: initiation, polymerization of sulfur in the presence of a modifier, stabilization of the obtained product [3].

Polysulfides are widely used in many fields of industry: in rubber vulcanization, anti-corrosion coatings, electrical engineering, obtaining heat-resistant materials, as binders in various fillers, in obtaining mesh polymers, etc. [4].

Sulfur reacts well with many organic substances [5]. For example, sulfur reacts with butane to form thiophene and hydrogen sulfide:

Reacts with aromatic compounds and releases organic sulfides and hydrogen sulfide:

Research has been conducted to obtain polysulfide using dicyclopentadiene as a modifier. In this case, a compound corresponding to the following general formula is formed:

This reaction is carried out for 4 hours in the range of 130-140^oS, and during the reaction, hydrogen sulfide is not released due to the binding of sulfur to dicyclopentadiene.

Materials and methods. Technical sulfur, glycerin, lower molecular polyethylene, aniline, phenol substances of the Mubarak gas processing plant were used as materials for research. The methods ISO 8332, ASTM D4569, ASTM D4574 were used to determine the solubility of polymer sulfur in toluene, stability to acid (H₂SO₄), heat stability (110^oC), ash content [6].

Results and their analysis. As a result of the conducted research, QMPE and propantriol were selected as modifiers for obtaining polymer sulfur. Technical sulfur was heated at a temperature of 125-130^oC. During heating, propantriol in the amount of 3% of the sulfur mass, low molecular weight polyethylene in the amount of 0.5% were added and mixed for 80 minutes. It was raised to 160 ^oC without stopping mixing and stirred for 320 minutes without changing this temperature. At high temperatures, glycerin releases a molecule of water to form acrolein. Acrolein undergoes a copolymerization reaction with sulfur.

The combined use of QMPE and propantriol as modifiers ensured a 50% yield in 5 hours. As a result of further increasing the duration of the reaction, it was proved that it is possible to obtain polymer sulfur with a yield of 60 % (Table 1).

Table 1

Physico-mechanical properties of synthesized polymer sulfur and HDOT20 polymer sulfur

Test indicators	Unit of measurement	Inspection method	Indicator name		Compliance with ISO 8332, ISO 8332, ASTM D4569, ISO 8332
			HDOT20	In practice	
Insoluble sulfur	%	ISO 8332	≥92.0	60	It didn't fit
Acid tolerance H₂SO₄	%	ASTM D4569	≤0.05	0,024	Fits
Heat resistance 110^oC	%	ISO 8332	≥72.00	83	Fits
Ash level	%	ASTM D4574	≤0.30	0,10	Fits

Table 1 presents the results of testing polymer sulfur according to the requirements of ISO 8332, ASTM D4569, ISO 8332, ASTM D4574.

Diagram of dependence of time and temperature changes of polymer sulfur was obtained on the basis of sulfur, propantriol (glycerin), lower molecular polyethylene in the ratio of 100:3:0.5 mass.

Figure 1. 60% yield of sulfur, propanetriol, lower molecular weight polyethylene when the reaction was carried out at 160 °C.

Diagram of dependence of time and temperature changes of polymer sulfur was obtained on the basis of sulfur, aniline and phenol in a mass ratio of 100:1.5:3.

As can be seen from Figure 2, polymer sulfur was formed with a yield of 25% after a reaction in the presence of phenol and aniline and lasting 180 minutes at 150 °C. In this reaction, aniline also acts as an initiator.

Conclusion. It was found that the use of a mixture of glycerin:QMPE in a mass ratio of 6/1 as a modifier in the production of polymer sulfur increases the yield of the reaction by up to 60 %. The polymer sulfur extraction reaction was found to produce high-performance products at a temperature of 158⁰S – 160⁰C and continued for 400 minutes.

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